

Perception about the Organizational Culture Among The Employees' Working in Private Sector Bank at Rajapalayam

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Abstract

An organizational culture is values, beliefs, norms, systems, habits, vision, environment etc, while following this culture the employees have their own perception. Perception deals with the way in which something is regarded, understood, or interpreted. An organizational culture is a social reality that signals to employees what they should do, feel and think. The objective of this study was to find out the organizational culture that determine the various factor such as, (openness, confrontation, trust, authenticity, precaution, autonomy, collaboration, experimentation organization commitment) and the impact of socio demographic variable with respect to the employees' perception towards the organizational culture in private bank sector. Perception differs from person to person. If the employee have the positive perception towards the organizational culture then their performance and attitude is good. The employee have the negative perception towards the organizational culture they will affect the performance it will also reflect the organization motive. The main aim of this study is to analysis the employees' perspective towards existing organizational culture in private sector bank. So, the researcher has proposed to undertake this study to overcome the above issues.

Keywords: Employees' Perception, Organizational Culture, Private bank.

Introduction

A bank is a financial institution that provides banking and other financial services to their customers. A bank is generally understood as an institution which provides fundamental banking services such as accepting deposits and providing loans. There are also non-banking institutions that provide certain banking services without meeting the legal definition of a bank. Banks are a subset of the financial services industry. The banking sector is the section of the economy devoted to the holding of financial assets for others, investing those financial assets as leverage to create more wealth and the regulation of those activities by both private and government banks.

Employee perception is a process by which individuals organize and interpret their sensory impressions in order to give meaning to their environment. Perception is not necessarily based on reality, but is merely a perspective from a particular individual's view of a situation. In dealing with the concept of organization culture,

perception becomes important because, people’s behavior is based on their perception of what reality is, not on reality itself; the world as it is perceived is the world that is behaviorally important. Human nature can be very simple, yet very complex too. An understanding and appreciation of this is no pre-requisite to effective employee perception in the workplace and therefore effective management and leadership. There is a known fact that without perception, nothing can be done in an organization and for doing any task we need a perception which is accepted by all the employees in an organization. It is the key for the manager to make her team work and get the better output for the organization. The perception helps each and every individual in the organization to carry the things in different ways as the organization needs different perceptions to make successful results.

Employee perception can be described as an organization brand and personality. It’s based on believe and stand for, and what makes the company unique. It can be related to the organization culture has everything to do with how employees, prospective employees, and the public perceive in the organization. The Organizational culture is a system of shared assumptions, values, and beliefs, which governs how people behave in organizations.

Objective

- To study the employees’ perception towards organization culture in private sector bank
- To study the existing culture of the organization and employees’ perception
- To study the relationship between socio demographic factor and organizational culture factor

Review of Literature

Maya.M, Dr. R. Thamilselvan (2012) carried out the study to identify the employee’s opinion and management strategies towards the talent management in the organization. It is not necessary that money is the only reason of leaving the organization but the dysfunctional company culture is also one of the main reasons for the same. The major strategies such as Job rotation and New Assignment, Alternative Work Schedule (AWS), Reward and Recognition system, Retention bonus/ scheme are the more acceptable by the majority of the employees in the IT organizations.

Sanjay Gaur, Dr. Awadhesh Bhardwaj (2013), reported that there are lot of Human Resource functions, the scholar collected the data from 200 nos. respondents and response rate was 100% from various organization located at Jaipur, Rajasthan which includes Banks, Manufacturing units, Export divisions, Govt. organizations, Educational institutes, Insurance companies, IT sectors, Hotels and Hospitals. Although there are various Human Resource functions are being carried out in all the organization. The employees do not perceive them equally important such as Performance Appraisal, Training, Executive Development and Career Planning etc. but not indifferent some function like Planning & Procurement, Development, Compensation, Integration and maintenance. It is desirable that the HR systems must be transparent and shared perceptions about the work culture and behaviors that management expects supports and rewards.

Viresh Mathur, Nair Manju (2013) revealed that Tyre industries should be pro-active for the development of philosophy Industrial Relation Management. The workers should be involve for sharing their views about their working conditions, welfare measures, encourage providing their valuable and innovative suggestions or ideas for improving the productivity and profitability of the organization. The culture of empathically approach should be adhered for resolving the issues of the workmen.

Crispen chipunza, Bulelwa malo (2017), conducted their study on the organizational culture and job satisfaction among academic professionals at a South African University of technology, from the data analysis, academic employees had positive views on the culture at the existing institution. They have gently satisfied with their jobs and there was a moderate relationship between

organizational culture and job satisfaction. The study recommends that management ensures that every employee understands and identifies with the culture of the institution, as organizational relates to employee behavior.

Statement of the Problem

An organizational culture is values, beliefs, norms, systems, habits, vision, environment etc, while following this culture the employees have their own perception. Perception of organizational culture depends up on the employees'. Most of the employees working in the bank sector having many perception about the new technology interfering, Working hours, atmosphere changed, insurance policy target, collection of loan amount, especially for female worker they are facing many problems about this organization culture. Perception is differing from person to person, gender to gender. If the perception is different in the organization it will affect the performance of the employees. So, overcome these problem banks have focus on their employees' perception.

Research Methodology

- Descriptive research design is used in this study.
- Sampling method used for the study is convenient random sampling.
- Primary data was collected from private sector bank in rajapalayam. Secondary data was collected from various journals, book and website.
- Sample size is 150. There are 150 employees from private sector bank are taken for the study.
- Statistical tools such as percentage analysis, multiple regressions, and Friedman test.

Analysis and Interpretation

Percentage Analysis

Table 1

Demographic Factors	Category	Percentage of the respondents
1. Gender	Male	60.7
	Female	39.3
	Total	100.0
2. Age	20-30	42.7
	31-40	38.7
	41-50	12.7
	51-60	6.0
	Total	100.0
3. Experience	1-3 years	64.0
	4-7 years	26.7
	8-15 years	6.7
	Above 15 years	2.7
	Total	100.0

Source: Primary data

From the above table, it is inferred that 61% of the respondent are male, 43% are belongs to age group of 20-30, 64% of the respondents are 1-3 years of experience.

Friedman Test-I

Null hypothesis H02: There is no difference in the ranks of the perception of employees about organizational culture in private sector banks.

Alternate hypothesis HA2: There is difference in the ranks of the perception of employees about organizational culture in private sector banks.

Table 2

Organizational culture	Mean Rank	N Value	P Value
Organizational goal	4.23	150	0.000
Organizational values and beliefs	3.61		
Communication network	6.10		
Rectify employees grievances	3.56		
Freedom of choosing method of work	4.18		
Implementation of new idea	4.80		
Job responsibility	2.70		
Co-ordination	6.81		

Source: Result computed through SPSS package

Table shows that computed p value less than, the above null hypothesis are rejected at 5% level of significance. Hence it is concluded that there is difference in the ranks of the perception of employees about organizational culture in private sector banks. The mean rank of job responsibility and rectify employees grievances got its Minimum value. This indicates that respondents have given low rank for job responsibility and rectify employees’ grievances.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis is the widely used analytical models of association prominent in market research. Multiple regression analysis attempts to study the relationship between dependent variable and a set of independent variables. The linear equation used for a regression analysis is

$$Y = B_0 + B_1 X_1 + B_2 X_2 + B_3 X_3 \dots\dots\dots$$

Where Y is the predicted score, X1 is the score on the first predictor variable, X2 is the score on the second, etc. Bo is a constant. B1, B2, B3 are the regression coefficients, and these coefficients gives the estimated change in the dependent variable associated with a unit change in the corresponding independent variable, with the condition that other independent variables remains constant.

Multiple regression analysis is between the gender with the positive and negative variables such as freedom of method of work, regular feedback about their performance, innovation or changes by top management, objectives is joint effort of superior and subordinate, opportunity to think and express freely, organization have common values and beliefs, new idea are encouraged in organization, working together is important to achieve goals and target, flow of ideas between work group, employees in organization perform down procedures and standards, clear communication channel available in organization, strict principles is used and follow by employees, customer are very important in organization, attention is given to employees grievances, job responsibility are clearly defined.

Table 3.1 Summary of regression model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.446	0.199	0.108	0.463

- a. Predictors: (Constant), job responsibilities are clearly defined, attention is given to employees grievances, opportunity to think and express freely, flow of ideas between work group, Regular feedback about their performance, objectives is joint effort of superior and subordinate, organization have common values and beliefs, working together is important to achieve goals and target, strict discipline is used and follow by employees, customer are very important in organization, new idea are encouraged in organization, clear communication channel available in organization, employees in organization perform down procedures and standards, Freedom method of working, Innovation or changes by top management.

The multiple correlation coefficient $R = 0.446$ indicates that there is a correlation between the gender and the relationship management and the variables predicted by the regression model. The Adjusted R square value accounts for 10.8% of variance.

Table 3.2 ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	7.086	15	0.472	2.201	0.009
Residual	28.551	133	0.215		
Total	35.638	148			

b. Dependent variable: Gender

ANOVA table provides the value with F-test (2.201) which accepts the null hypothesis at 0.009 significant levels.

Table 3.3 Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Unstandardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.217	.451		4.916	.000
Freedom method of working	.114	.065	.250	1.746	.083
Regular feedback about their performance	-.028	.055	-.050	-.518	.605
Innovation or changes by top management	.099	.068	.210	1.453	.148
objectives is joint effort of superior and subordinate	-.136	.060	-.205	-2.263	.025
opportunity to think and express freely	-.086	.046	-.162	-1.853	.066
organization have common values and beliefs	-.039	.061	-.063	-.637	.525
new idea are encouraged in organization	-.076	.048	-.184	-1.593	.113
working together is important to achieve goals and target	.043	.056	.069	.766	.445
flow of ideas between work group	-.123	.056	-.181	-2.183	.031

employees in organization perform down procedures and standards	-.112	.048	-.253	-2.321	.022
clear communication channel available in organization	.010	.081	.013	.118	.906
strict discipline is used and follow by employees	.057	.059	.097	.964	.337
customer are very important in organization	.157	.098	.159	1.603	.111
attention is given to employees grievances	-.089	.066	-.129	-1.352	.179
job responsibilities are clearly defined	-.065	.083	-.092	-.786	.433

a. Dependent variable: gender

Interpretation

Positive correlation The positive variables such as ‘freedom of method of working’, ‘innovation or changes by top management’, working together is important to achieve goals and target’, ‘clear communication channel available in organization’, strict discipline is used and follow by employees’, ‘customer are very important in organization’.

Negative correlation The negative variables such as ‘regular feedback about their performance’, ‘objectives is joint effort of superior and subordinate’, ‘opportunity to think and express freely’, ‘organization have common values and beliefs’, ‘new idea are encouraged in organization’, ‘flow of idea between work group’, ‘employees in organization perform down procedures and standard’, ‘attention is given to employees grievances’, ‘job responsibility are clearly defined’.

Findings

Percentage analysis

- Majority of the respondent are male (61%), 43% of the respondent are belong to the age of (20-30), 64% of the respondent have 1-3 years of experience.

Friedman Test

- Majority of the respondents’ the mean rank of job responsibility and rectify employees grievances got minimum value. This indicates that respondents have given low rank of job responsibility and rectify employees’ grievances.

Multiple-regression analysis

- In predictive validity, R2 Model Summary reveals that 46.3% of variance in overall perception can be predicted from the combination of gender dimensions. The “freedom of method of work” dimension is the main predictor.

Suggestion

- Management should properly concentrate on rectify the grievances of employees’. That organization have proper platform for rectify the grievances. Remedy is given to employees through the top level management or supervisors.
- Organization should not give more job responsibility to the employees’. If the employees have more responsibility may create the employees stress. So, the organization should reduce the employees’ responsibility.
- Organization has both positive and negative correlation. They should concentrate on their negative correlation to improve the employees’ satisfaction. Organization should concentrate mostly on co-ordination, communication, opportunity to perform, common values and beliefs, New idea generation and flow of idea.

Conclusion

Organization culture is central to any activity in the organization. The study of Organization culture in an organization is a powerful predictor of such organizational outcomes such as job performance, job commitment, job satisfaction, company productivity and important profitability. Employee perception towards the organization culture employees what should feel or think about the organization. However there are few areas were the employee's expectations needs to be bridged with the organization culture for which researcher has put forth few valuable suggestions for consideration of the management.

Endnotes

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Questionnaire

Respected Sir/Madam

I am C.SURATHA PhD Research scholar (full time) in business administration, V.H.N.S.N. College (Autonomous) Virudhunagar. As, a part of my project. I would like to gather some information from you to complete my study. I would be obliged if you co-operate with me in filling questionnaire. The data collected from you only used for academic purposes only and be kept confidential.

I. Personal Information

1. Name : _____

2. Sex : a) Male b) Female

3. Age of respondent :
a) 20-30 b) 31-40 c) 41-50 d) 51-60

4. Level of education :
a) school b) diploma c) UG d) PG

5. For how long have you been working with your present organization?
a) 1-3 years b) 4-7 years c) 8-15years d) Above 15 years

6. Marital Status : a) Married b) Unmarried

7. Monthly Income :

- a) Below Rs.8000 b) Rs.8000- Rs.10000 c) Rs.10000-15000 d) Rs.15000-20000
 e) Above Rs.20000

Tick the Employees’ Perception on Organization Culture

Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
8. In this organization employees are given freedom to choose their own method of working					
9. In this organization employees receive regular feedback about their performance					
10. Organization innovation or changes are largely ordered by top management					
11. Organization setting up of objectives is a joint effort of superior and subordinates					
12. Employees are given much opportunity to think and express freely					
13. Employees in this organization have common values and beliefs					
14. Employees who come out with new ideas are encouraged in this organization					
15. Employees here strongly believe that working together is important to achieve goals and targets					
16. Our work place is designed to promote the flow of ideas between work group					
17. Employees in this organization perform their work tasks as per laid down procedures and standards					
18. Clear communication channels are available to pass information to any level in this organization					
19. Strict discipline is in-built in this organization and the employees are used to it					
20. Everyone in this organization believes that customers are very important					
21. Prompt attention is given to employees grievances in this organization					
22. Job responsibilities are clearly defined for all the jobs in this organization					